

USING FACEBOOK AS A TOOL TO IMPROVE WRITING SKILLS FOR TERTIARY STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this briefing paper is to review the benefits of using Facebook; the social network site, from the aspect of exploiting its function to support the educational mission. Specifically, a closer observation was made to see how Facebook pages could be used to help improve students' writing skills in teaching and learning English. The paper also provides information regarding one particular "hot potato", namely the befriending of students, and to explore tertiary learners' attitudes when using Facebook to help them improve their English, especially their writing skills. A group of ten first-year English- majored students were chosen to give their response on the issue and serve as a pilot experiment. Follow this, a proposal of some pre-designed writing activities is offered to writing teachers, as well as those who have an interest in this field, to exploit the benefit of technology in terms of improving their students' writing skills. Finally, some anticipated problems are drawn out for both teachers and students.

Keywords: writing skills, writing tasks, outside classroom, language students, social networking site.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Context of using Facebook

Today's youth were born into a digital world. This is creating a vibrant world full of interactivity and learning, where young people make new things, improve their creativity and enrich their writing skills. The classroom is somewhat different from what it used to be not long ago. Indeed, as the South West Grid for Learning's (SWGFL) 'Facebook Advice' document (2010) states: "Facebook is a global social networking site used by 10% of the population on the planet. It's phenomenal popularity has been defined by the opportunities it gives its users to communicate, collaborate and share in a way that has never been possible before."

Recently, Vietnam was considered as the fastest-growing Facebook market in the world. Vietnam ranks 17th in the world in Facebook use immediately between Spain (16th) and Egypt (18th). In fact, there are more Facebook users in Vietnam than in Malaysia, Taiwan, Japan or South Korea. As of January 2014, there were 22 million Facebook users in Vietnam; a penetration rate of 65% of all Vietnamese netizens and 26% of the entire population are "facebooking". The current age distribution is 28% among students aged 13-18; 45% aged 18-25; and 19% students aged 25-35.

These numbers suggest that university students are the main users of Facebook. Also, the use of mobile is much more than non-mobile. It means that students do not always have to get a laptop to log in to Facebook. They can easily use their mobile device whenever and wherever they want to.

Therefore, the idea of using Facebook in Vietnamese to improve students' English skill is very feasible. Many educators in the world in general and in Vietnam in particular have not had a proper point of view about Facebook. They generally have a negative viewpoint towards this social networking site. Thus, it is very necessary to know what benefits Facebook can bring to our educational system.

1.2 Context of teaching writing skills

How to learn and practice writing skills has been considered as one of the most complex and difficult stage for some students as they often do not know how to explore ideas or even find the appropriate words to what they want to write about (Yahwang, 2010). To Nunan (2003:125), he claimed that writing are frequently accepted as being the last language skill to be acquired and it is widely considered a clearly complex activity process. Also, talking about this issue, Harmer (2007:57) added that teaching means to give someone knowledge or to instruct or to train someone; consequently, writing teachers are expected to help their students overcome this problem in an effective and accessible way. According to (Yahwang, 2010) teaching writing skills can be carried out in teaching a group, it's always a great idea to make use of the other students' ideas or lexical source in the class. Although writing practice sounds like an independent activity, the fact is sometimes the opposite. Therefore, a teacher can create and assign writing activities that requires the engagement of many students o take part in.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Facebook's Function

Social network sites can be defined as “web-based services that allow individuals to (1) construct a public or semi-public profile within a bounded system, (2) identify a list of other users with whom they share a connection, and (3) view and traverse their list of connections and those made by others within the system”. Social software or “Web 2.0” is used as a term to describe a platform in which content is created, shared, remixed, and passed along. To explore this function of Facebook in serving the learning purpose, students using Web 2.0 exercises actively participate in creating, evaluating, and transmitting, and assimilating knowledge.

2.2 Exploiting Facebook to support learning and teaching

Recently, many researchers have extended the study of the impact of Facebook to every aspect of our life. Some shed light into the ways of using Facebook as an effective educational tool. According to a study of Arkhom Bunloet et al. from Khon Kaen University in Thailand of July 2010, two top reasons why people use Facebook are: Having conversations with friends and reducing stress. The two most frequent activities that they use Facebook are: to post data, and using Facebook applications. The nature of Facebook helps people to relax and entertain themselves by its diverse functions and applications. On this theme, I think it would be an interesting idea if we can make study more relaxing and enjoyable. Students will have more fun while studying. Because Facebook is universally used, it can be applied in many countries in the world including developing and under developing countries. From my personal perspectives, it is worth giving it a try in Vietnam.

One more noteworthy advantage of Facebook is that we can create a small, closed group in which members with a shared goal or purpose can interact together within a more private and personal setting. Thus, for language educators, Facebook can offer “new and exciting ways” to impact students learning and development” (Jeness, 2011, p.54), help establish group cohesiveness

(Dorngei&Murphey, 2003) and foster learner autonomy (Benson, 2011) by members sharing their individual thoughts and ideas forums (Bray & Nur-Iswanti, 2013, p.34) outside the regular allotted time.

Andrew Boon and Daniel Beck also stated in their study for facilitating L2 usage outside of the classroom that: “students commented that Facebook increased their opportunities to use L2 outside the classroom. Students could interact with group members and teachers. Facebook also provided students with a convenient means to ask teachers questions outside of the regular class time, regarding homework tasks, or grammar and lexical usage”. Therefore, setting up new pages for language classes is feasible, especially English classes, as proposed in this paper.

Many schools, institutions, and universities apply Facebook in teaching and learning. For instance, the Department of Computer Engineering, Faculty of Engineering and Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Science, KhonKaen University, Thailand, together with Faculty of Informatics, Burapha University, Thailand, all use Facebook as a supplementary tool for teaching and learning in the field. These are some activities that they have used Facebook for:

Use of Facebook groups for formal courses

Advanced Computer Programing

XML and Web Sêvices

Programming for android

Use of Facebook group for advising students

Coordinating Groups of senior projects

Coordinating Groups of graduate students

Coordinating Groups of students who are interested in software competitions

They have presented an approach and shared experiences in using Facebook for teaching and learning in their faculties.

2.3 Using Facebook for feedback in English writing class

So far, Facebook feedback as a mean of learning English has been investigated in various studies with university to college students in both EFL and ESL classrooms worldwide. In particular, Suthiwartnarueput and Wasanasomsithi (2012) conducted an experimental study to investigate the effects of peer feedback on Facebook on students’ grammar and writing ability. It is concluded that the student participants in this study revealed their positive attitudes to using Facebook in their class at this social network offered them opportunities to engage in discussions with their teachers and other peers so as to enhance their English grammar and writing skill. In another experimental study by Wichadee (2013) share the same attention on exploring the effects of peer feedback on students’ writing performance. The results of the studies demonstrated positive outcomes achieved by the students in terms of significantly improving their writing ability and gaining their optimistic attitudes towards the use of Facebook for peer feedback.

With the same focus on Facebook peer feedback, the quasi-experimental study by and Alotumi (2015) was to determine the effects of online peer feedback through Close Grope Facebook on the students’ writing achievement. The research used quasi-experimental, non randomized control group, pre and post-test design and analysis of covariance to analyse data. The findings revealed the participants found this strategy beneficial and effective for their writing skill developments in

terms of helping them to be active learners, improving their confidence, improving their own writing by reading and commenting their peer's writing. One major challenge discussed in the study was that online peer feedback seems less effective in helping the student revise their language used and mechanics.

In short, it is noteworthy to notice that a great deal of research on using Facebook to support writing skills has been carried out worldwide. However, when viewing the literature in the Vietnam context, the literature on the educational use of Facebook is still nascent, and questions remain as to when and how to implement this new technology in order to reap the potential benefits, if it can indeed be achieved. Therefore, the current paper is to aim at filling the gap for research in the field. It can be considered at the testing phase and the foundation for further research carried out in the university context.

2.4 Participants' responses in piloting stage

It is hypothesized that students that are using the site for purely social reasons might be less inclined to participate in Facebook activities that relate to academic activity. On the other hand, those who have found social media to be useful in academic or professional tasks might be more inclined to participate in an academic application of Facebook. However, after a piloting survey carried out in a writing class at a Private university in Ho Chi Minh City, the researcher notice that there is a surprising result on students' willingness to engage with class material on a Facebook page. These are some of their deep attitudes:

"If teachers used Facebook to help us improve our writing kills, I think it would get our full participations".

"I suppose Facebook is a good way to shared information on learning materials."

"I will post to a Facebook page connected to a class if there is one official account."

"I would visit a Facebook page set up by a professor."

After some pilot experiments, it has been shown that many students quickly respond to teachers' posts and they also shared useful information. The advantages of using Facebook for teaching and learning are convenience, easy to use, and instant interaction. The only disadvantage that they encountered was being too open to the public.

The above-mentioned idea is just theory; in reality how many teachers can understand the deep needs of their students and to integrate their formal teaching in class into the relaxing classroom activities on Facebook or any other social network page? If a teacher can set up a trustworthy Facebook page, students would be more excited and less worried about using it. Also, it is important to make the applications of Facebook more interesting for students to participate in their academic activities.

3 PLANS FOR WRITING ACTIVITIES

These are some basic steps and activities that a teacher can apply to teaching English writing in English 10 – new version.

3.1 Setting up a Facebook page

The first thing that a teacher should do is to set up a dedicated Facebook group for the class. A Facebook group can allow students to create discussion boards, communicate with each other and

their teacher, and can be linked with online projects & other classroom groups. Teachers can use these groups to send out mass messages, reminders, and potentially even post homework assignments. The teacher should be sure that the language setting is in English because through the Facebook instructions, students can learn the language. As they log in possibly many times a day or even one time a day, they will acquire such language naturally.

In addition, rather than link a personal account as a teacher, it may be more appropriate to create a “class only” profile instead. It may be worth discussing digital citizenship with students beforehand, and ensure they friend this account after updating their own privacy settings. The page should be established at the beginning of the school year so that it creates a smooth and uninterrupted flow in-class English lessons. It is important for teacher to keep students posted about the lessons. If they are motivated, they would stay tuned to check the information.

After setting up a Facebook page for the class, the teacher should create an icebreaker activity on that web page. For example, he/she would post some questions about hobbies or organizing some outdoor activities for all class members to join in and then ask students to comment in English. By these starting questions, the teacher can successfully involve his/her students and foster them to participate actively.

3.2 Using Facebook features

Teacher should apply Facebook features to promote autonomous learning:

The Wall (Profile)

Chatting, video-chat, messages INBOX

Groups, pages

Events

Photos & Videos (with tagging)

Posted items (text and URLs, file attachment feature is available, 25mb maximum)

Shared items

Applications

4 SUGGESTED WRITING ACTIVITIES IN THE FACEBOOK GROUP

4.1 Writing summaries

Teachers can post a short article from the web related to the lesson and then ask students to write a brief summary of the article in a word processor. This activity aims at raising the critical thinking of students and improving the cohesion and coherence in their writing. They will practice how to summarize and paraphrase. Once they have their document ready, they should name it after their names for example: “summaryJuan.doc” and let them attach it on the group site. This activity improves writing summaries and reading comprehension.

4.2 Collective Story Telling

Teacher can try Collective Story Telling. He/she posts a series of pictures to the group, explaining that students should continue the sentence he/she has started (e.g. “A beautiful morning, in a

beautiful forest, a sparrow saw a worm in the ground...”), every student should write at least a paragraph. At the end the story should be revised and corrected if there are any mistakes.

4.3 Picture Descriptions

In this activity, teacher posts a picture to the group he/she has created; letting students comment on the picture and guessing what is in the picture? Where was it taken? How old is it? Etc. It is always a good idea to provide useful vocabulary to make the activity easier. Students comment on the picture and describe it using the useful vocabulary provided. If there is an English class the next day, the night before the teacher can post this picture and raise the questions: What might be the feelings of the man and the woman in this picture? The man and the woman do the same work, but they look different. Why?

After the picture is posted, the students will add comments. The teacher can join the discussion to warm up the atmosphere. There may be different points of view; this activity improves the critical thinking of students.

4.4 Picture Comparison

With this type of task, students can learn techniques to describe pictures. To start with, the teacher can post two slightly dissimilar pictures, then ask students to contrast the pictures posted, after some certain time, let every student comment on the picture, the teacher can also provide useful vocabulary to facilitate the activity. At the end of the discussion, the teacher should give feedback to the students.

4.5 Collective Writing (Mini-project)

The teacher can ask students to work cooperatively to write about their school, a tour destination, a place they have visited or topics they know. For example, about Cultural Diversity, teacher will organize an activity named Around the World. The teacher will divide the class into groups and each group will be in charge of an online presentation about a famous city in the world. They have to look for the information, the picture and they will prepare a written introduction about that city attached to the pictures. Every member of the group has to be in charge of completing the writing of their part. This activity will help students to increase their collaborative learning.

4.6 Writing Portfolio

In order to tackle writing portfolio tasks, teachers are expected to put a lot of effort into expanding their pedagogical portfolio, to promote active learning through a learning community, and to test the effectiveness of on-line learning communities through this social network. Students can write about what they can learn from the classroom. They also can write about the advantages and disadvantages that Facebook bring to them. Using that portfolio, teachers can adjust the way they are managing and organizing the activities on Facebook.

5 ASSESSMENT

The nature of Facebook is not to study but to keep contacts and entertain one's self. It is not a good idea for teachers to try to force students to study seriously and competitively via Facebook. However, Facebook is a good supplementary tool for learning, in this case for learning English. I strongly recommend that teachers should not evaluate the study process via Facebook too severely. Instead, use Facebook as a tool to motivate students and foster their learning process, especially to improve the writing skills of students gradually and naturally. This is just to aid the classroom learning activities. Otherwise, if teachers don't control or evaluate the learning process via Facebook learning, the implementation of Facebook in learning will not be successful. So, this is a really controversial matter.

How can teachers balance the nature of learning and the nature of Facebook?

This question is quite hard to answer. In my proposal, my main purpose is to improve students' learning in an unforced and natural manner. However, to make students more conscious about what they do, I will give marks to them. The mark that students receive accounts for the 15-minute test and a writing competition accounts for the 1 hour test. Students will be motivated to take part because of the assessment. I will focus more on the quality of the writing not the enthusiasm of students. There should be some rules for the class page, for instance, avoiding using Vietnamese language. This is a good way to foster students' use of English.

6 ANTICIPATED PROBLEMS

There might be some problems while this proposal is applying in the real life context.

Teachers can be overloaded with work. They have to read through the writing of students to assess them and their writing ability. If teachers want to check the spelling, it is quite hard for them to check on Facebook because they cannot highlight the mistakes of every single student. To improve this shortcoming, teachers should not post too many assignments. Maybe there should be one post for one unit which is taught in 3 classes. Teachers can take note of the most common mistakes that students encounter and then write them on the blackboard in the class. In this way, it is less time-

consuming when checking mistakes. Students may feel bored after many posts from teachers. Teachers should vary the way they post and change the activities.

7 CONCLUSION

Facebook's networking and social communication capabilities increase both teacher-student and student-student interaction by using web-based communication. Facebook helps instructors connect with their students about assignments, upcoming events, useful links, and samples of work outside of the classroom. In this specific context, students will improve their writing skills including those considered difficult skills. Many students find writing in English tough because it has a different style from Vietnamese writing. Therefore, by practicing writing activities on Facebook, students can naturally build their skills in writing.

It is undeniable that using Facebook will improve the learner-centeredness and learner autonomy. In addition, pictures can be used within the text in order to motivate students and stimulate their critical thinking. More tasks which develop the learning autonomy are focused on. The activities are very diverse. However, the time allotted in the class is limited. It will be a real challenge for both teachers and students to go through all the tasks effectively within the class time. There should be more extra time allocated.

Finally, the hope of this paper is to receive some further suggestions or deeper investigations on implementing Facebook as an educational tool in order to help learners make use of the most benefit of technology advancement to master their language, specifically their writing skills as mentioned in this paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] Alotumi, M. (2015). Facebook Interaction (FBI) and essay writing pre-task: Yemeni EFL students' perceptions, attitudes and challenges. *Attitudes and Challenges (February 27, 2015)*.
- [2] Ajjan, H., & Hartshorne, R. (2008). Investigating faculty decisions to adopt Web 2.0 technologies: Theory and empirical tests. *The internet and higher education, 11(2)*, 71-80.
- [3] Beetham, H., & Sharpe, R. (2013). *Rethinking pedagogy for a digital age: Designing for 21st century learning*. routledge.
- [4] Cothrel, J., & Williams, R. L. (1999). On-line communities: helping them form and grow. *Journal of knowledge management, 3(1)*, 54-60.
- [5] Debatin, B., Lovejoy, J. P., Horn, A. K., & Hughes, B. N. (2009). Facebook and online privacy: Attitudes, behaviors, and unintended consequences. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication, 15(1)*, 83-108.
- [6] Ellison, N. B., Steinfield, C., & Lampe, C. (2007). The benefits of Facebook "friends:" Social capital and college students' use of online social network sites. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication, 12(4)*, 1143-1168.
- [7] Harmer, Jeremy. (2007). *The Practice of English Language Teaching*. London: Longman.
- [8] Hew, K. F. (2011). Students' and teachers' use of Facebook. *Computers in Human Behavior, 27(2)*, 662-676.

- [9] Hewitt, A., & Forte, A. (2006). Crossing boundaries: Identity management and student/faculty relationships on the Facebook. *Poster presented at CSCW, Banff, Alberta*, 1-2.
- [10] Klamma, R., Chatti, M. A., Duval, E., Hummel, H., Hvannberg, E. T., Kravcik, M., ...& Scott, P. (2007). Social software for life-long learning. *Journal of Educational Technology & Society*, 10(3), 72-83.
- [11] Lampe, C., Wohn, D. Y., Vitak, J., Ellison, N. B., & Wash, R. (2011). Student use of Facebook for organizing collaborative classroom activities. *International Journal of Computer-Supported Collaborative Learning*, 6(3), 329-347.
- [12] Lenhart, A., Purcell, K., Smith, A., & Zickuhr, K. (2010). Social Media & Mobile Internet Use among Teens and Young Adults. Millennials. *Pew Internet & American Life Project*.
- [13] Mason, R. (2006). Learning technologies for adult continuing education. *Studies in Continuing Education*, 28(2), 121-133.
- [14] Mazer, J. P., Murphy, R. E., & Simonds, C. J. (2007). I'll see you on "Facebook": The effects of computer-mediated teacher self-disclosure on student motivation, affective learning, and classroom climate. *Communication Education*, 56(1), 1-17.
- [15] Mazman, S. G., & Usluel, Y. K. (2010). Modeling educational usage of Facebook. *Computers & Education*, 55(2), 444-453.
- [16] McLoughlin, C., & Lee, M. J. (2007, December). Social software and participatory learning: Pedagogical choices with technology affordances in the Web 2.0 era. In *ICT: Providing choices for learners and learning. Proceedings ascilite Singapore 2007* (pp. 664-675).
- [17] Rosenblum, D. (2007). What anyone can know: The privacy risks of social networking sites. *IEEE Security & Privacy*, (3), 40-49.
- [18] Selwyn, N. (2007). 'Screw Blackboard... do it on Facebook!': an investigation of students' educational use of Facebook. *Ponencia. En: Poke*.
- [19] Suthiwartnarueput, T., & Wasanasomsithi, P. (2012). Effects of using Facebook as a medium for discussions of English grammar and writing of low-Intermediate EFL students. *Electronic Journal of Foreign Language Teaching*, 9(2).
- [20] Torres, A. M. (2012). Social networking and online privacy: Facebook users' perceptions. *Irish Journal of Management*.
- [21] Towner, T. L., VanHorn, A. M., & Parker, S. L. (2007). Facebook: Classroom tool for a classroom community. In *annual meeting of the Midwest Political Science Association, Palmer House Hotel, Chicago, IL*.
- [22] Wodzicki, K., Schwämmlein, E., & Moskaliuk, J. (2012). "Actually, I Wanted to Learn": Study-related knowledge exchange on social networking sites. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 15(1), 9-14.
- [23] Yahwang, Nik. (2010). *A protocol analysis of the planning processes of Japanese writers writing in English*. Tanglaw . Manila, Philippines: De La Salle University Press.
- [25] Wichadee, S. (2013). Peer feedback on Facebook: The use of social networking websites to develop writing ability of undergraduate students. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 14(4), 260-270.